

An Investigation into Learner's Autonomy at an Institution in Vietnam

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ABSTRACT: The study employed a mixed method research design to investigate the self-perceived levels of learners' autonomy at the institution where the researcher works. The study also explores the teachers' support in fostering students' autonomy. In addition, the study attempts to determine the relationship between genders, learning styles and the learners' levels of autonomy. The main findings reveal that the level of learners' autonomy where the study was conducted was at medium level ($M = 2.66$ out of 5.0 scale). In terms of the students' perception of their teachers' roles in fostering students' autonomy, the finding of the current study reveals that it was quite supportive ($M = 3.29$ out of 5.0 scale). The finding also indicated that the difference in level of autonomy is not significant between male and female students ($M = 2.667$ for male compared with $M = 2.668$ for female students). Finally, the result showed that there a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between students with different learning styles. To be specifically, the students who prefer kinesthetic learning style possess the highest level of autonomy ($M = 2.75$) compared with $M = 2.60$ and 2.59 for visual and individual learning style students. $M=2.72$; $M=2.69$ and $M=2.62$ are the level of autonomy for group, tactile and auditory students respectively.

KEYWORDS: Learners' autonomy, teachers' supports, fostering learners' autonomy, gender, learning styles.

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1. Background to the study

Learners' autonomy (hereinafter LA) has been determined by Nguyen & Habók (2020) as a solution to the difficulties of the 21st century education in terms of theories, learning styles and strategies, and approaches capable of meeting labour market needs. According to Le (2013), the researcher expressed his desire for enhancing LA in the background of tertiary education of Vietnam in order to contribute to an active workforce that capable of lifelong learning and adapting to new development and changes in the world.

In the present days, crimes are not bounded in a country but on global scales. Public security agents should be armed with languages to deal with varieties of criminals. English is the most widely taught language at police institutions. Regardless of investments and contributions, English proficiency among trainee officers has been far below expectation, especially for non-English major students. Due to the importance of LA in the tertiary education in general and at The People's Police Academy of Vietnam (hereinafter PPA) in particular, it is necessary to get information about how students themselves perceive LA and some factors that impact on their own autonomy. Therefore, I conduct this research, which is title "*An investigation into the first-year non-English major students' autonomy at a People's Police Training Institution*", in the hope of making the contribution to the further development of LA in language learning.

1.2. Problem statement

It is a matter of fact that learners' autonomy and the fostering role of teachers in many institutions are not receiving adequate attention as part of the educational context. Lindley (1986; 136) suggests that an educational system which was geared to promote widespread autonomy amongst its pupils would provide an environment which stimulated critical self-awareness, a desire to question received wisdom, and self-directedness; and most schools are unable to provide this.

An investigation into levels of autonomy among students and the teacher's promotion of learners' autonomy is vital in creating a stable and more effective learning environment.

1.3. Significance of the study

It is obvious that learner's autonomy plays a significant role in language learning by making the learners take responsibility and make decisions for their own learning. However, what can they do to help themselves move towards the goal of personal autonomy is vital. Besides, understanding the roles of teachers in promoting learners' autonomy is no less important.

This study is conducted at a People's Police institutions where autonomy, self-directedness, self-regulation are especially dignified. The study on completion would provide a reference for language teachers at PPA about students' autonomy so that they may provide

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variety of teaching techniques or appropriate teaching activities to motivate students' self-esteem to make their students more autonomous in learning English. In addition, teachers are expected to recognize their roles in fostering their learners' autonomy.

1.4. Purposes of the study

Students who enrol in police institutions should be more autonomous than other students because of their future career which deals with unexpected situations in everyday lives. However, Observations indicate that there are low levels of student anatomy in foreign language learning, in this case, English language learning. The primary purpose of this study is to determine the self-perceived levels of anatomy among first year students at a police training institutions in Hanoi, Vietnam. The secondary purpose of the study is figure out how students perceive the roles of teachers in fostering learners' autonomy. Finally, the study investigates how learners' autonomy is affected by genders, learning styles of the individuals. The independent variables can be defined as genders, learning styles of the students. The dependent variable is the learners' autonomy of the first year students at PPA.

1.5. Research questions

From the above mentioned purposes, the study attempted to answer the following research questions:

- 1.5.1. *What are the perceived levels of autonomy of the first year non-English major students at the People's Police Academy?*
- 1.5.2. *What are the students' perceptions towards the roles of teachers in fostering their autonomy?*
- 1.5.3. *Is there a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between genders?*
- 1.5.4. *Is there a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between students with different learning styles?*

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Theoretical framework

Learner autonomy has been defined somewhat differently from different perspectives. However, the most widely accepted definition is that "autonomous learners understand the purpose of their learning programme, explicitly accept responsibility for their learning, share in the setting of learning goals, take initiatives in planning and executing learning activities, and regularly review their learning and evaluate its effectiveness (cf. Holec 1981, Little 1991). In other words, there is a consensus that the practice of learner autonomy requires insight, a positive attitude, a capacity for reflection, and a readiness to be proactive in self-management and in interaction with others. This working definition captures the challenge of learner autonomy: a holistic view of the learner that requires us to engage with the cognitive, metacognitive, affective and social dimensions of language learning and to worry about how they interact with one another.

Learner autonomy is, however, a problematic term because it is widely confused with self-instruction. It is also a slippery concept because it is notoriously difficult to define precisely. The rapidly expanding literature has debated, for example, whether learner autonomy should be thought of as capacity or behaviour; whether it is characterised by learner responsibility or learner control; whether it is a psychological phenomenon with political implications or a political right with psychological implications; and whether the development of learner autonomy depends on a complementary teacher autonomy (for a comprehensive survey, see Benson 2001).

Literally, the word of autonomy is derived from a Greek word "autonomous", which is auto meaning "self" and "nomos" meaning "rule or law", (Tin, 2012:52).

2.2. Autonomy in language classroom

Classroom-based approaches aiming to foster autonomy are based on providing the learners the opportunities to make decisions concerning the management of their own learning. According to Benson (2001), as cited in Egel, (2009: 202), positive results gain where the learner has been encouraged to take a certain amount of control over the planning and assessment of classroom learning have shown that learners are able to exercise control over their learning opportunity as necessary support. He also discusses the implications of the rise of "classroom autonomy" has led to a re-conceptualization of autonomy as a "usable" construct for teachers who want to help their learners develop autonomy without necessarily challenging constraints of classroom and curriculum organization to which they are subject.

Learner autonomy in language learning has been viewed in many different ways. One way it has been viewed is as a situation in which the learner is "totally responsible" for all the decisions he/she makes for their learning (Dickinson, 1987, p.11). This view signifies full autonomy, which is referred to a situation in which the learner is independent and learns with the absence of the teacher. However, Little's (1990) interpretation of learner autonomy is contradictory to this. For him, learner autonomy should signify neither the teacher taking no responsibility nor the learner working with absolute freedom and in isolation from the teacher and peers. Being completely independent or, in other words, having a total detachment is not an indicator of autonomy.

From another angle, the concept of autonomy signifies learner's expansive approach to the learning process rather than a specified style of teaching or learning (Benson, 2001, p. 1). Benson and Voller (1997) specify these processes where learner autonomy is used in five ways in language education, they list these ways in which autonomy concept is used, as follows:

1. Situations in which learners study entirely on their own;
2. A set of skills which can be learned and applied in self-directed learning;

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3. An inborn capacity which is suppressed by institutional education;
4. Exercise of learners' responsibility for their own learning;
5. The right of learners to determine the direction of their own learning. (p. 2)

2.3. Teacher's roles in fostering autonomy in classroom?

It is important for teachers to promote levels of autonomy for learners. In language learning, this entails detachment from one's own learning, development of linguistic and metalinguistic awareness, and creating an ability to reflect on one's own learning procedure. Apart from being aware of their own learning, autonomous learners also need to practice collaboration with teachers, learners, and native speakers or more experienced peers (Schwienhorst, 2012) in order to take control of their learning in various learning situations.

Dam (2011) sees the development of learner autonomy as a move from an often totally teacher-directed teaching environment to a possible learner-directed learning environment (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Developing learner autonomy – a simplified model (Dam, 2011, p. 41)

According to Dam (2011) the role of the teacher could be choosing personal aims, activities, partners, organization of work, or ways of evaluation. In this connection, the teacher is responsible for presenting her learners with the demands outlined in the curricular guidelines for their learning within which they can set their individual goals. It is also her responsibility to establish some kind of transparent structure for a lesson or a teaching/learning sequence which the learners can take over, partly or completely, in due course (p. 45).

The role of a teacher can also vary in autonomous learning based on her/his interaction with learners. According to Voller (1997), a teacher can take on three different roles as a *facilitator*, *counsellor*, and *resource*. The language teacher may act as a facilitator who initiates and supports decision-making processes, a counsellor who responds to the on-going needs of individuals, and a resource who makes his or her knowledge and expertise available to the learners in times of need.

Little (1995) asserts that learner autonomy depends on teacher autonomy in two senses. First, it is unreasonable to expect teachers to foster their learner autonomy if they themselves do not know what makes an autonomous learner. Second, in determining the initiatives they take in their classrooms, teachers have to be able to apply to their teaching those same reflective and self-managing methods that they apply to their learning.

Fostering autonomy in classroom brings many benefits for language learners. It makes students aware that the teacher will not always be present to lead the learning process and therefore helps the former to become more effective (Cotterall, 1995); autonomy makes learners become motivated and enthusiastic towards learning (Dickinson, 1995; Fukuda, Hiroshi, & Takeushi, 2011; Littlejohn, 1985); an autonomous student is more secure in his/her learning (Joiner as cited in McCafferty, 1981; Scharle & Szabó, 2000), and therefore it is plausible that he/she will, eventually, be prepared for functioning effectively in society (Cotterall, 1995). In short, teachers play an important role in establishing an environment where the learners are being prepared for taking over responsibility for their own learning.

2.4. Learners' roles in building up autonomy

Talking about learners' roles in becoming autonomous learners, Benson (2008, p. 26) put it in a question as "*What can learners do to help themselves move towards the goal of personal autonomy?*" Autonomous learners are those who believe that they are capable of organizing and performing a course of action required to achieve success (Bandura, 1997). Little (1990) defines it as "a capacity for detachment, critical reflection, decision-making, and independent action" (p. 7). Holec (1981) suggest that autonomous learners are fully aware of and understand their course objectives, accept the learning goals, and agree to take responsibility. When an autonomous learner exercises his/her learner autonomy by performing a number of learning management behaviours, he/she is able

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to take control rather than take charge of his/her learning processes. Horváth (2005) suggests that there are two interrelated elements in autonomy construction, namely *cognitive* and *behavioural*. The former is related to the psychological aspect (what learners believe); and the latter is related to their behavioural actions (what they do). In an investigation on the behavioural and cognitive aspects of learner autonomy, Horváth (2005) provides more specific examples of each element. The first is associated with management behaviours such as choosing materials, methods, time, and partners with which to learn (O'Malley & Chamot, 1990; Oxford & Shearin, 1994). The latter is connected with the conscious efforts of learners such as plan making, monitoring, reflecting, and assessing which trigger and drive the performance of learning behaviours (Dickinson, 1992, 1995; Littlewood, 1996). Horváth also suggests that the most important values of the cognitive component are reflection, self-reflection, evaluation, and self-evaluation. These are constantly used by an investigated sample of postgraduate interpreter trainees. In addition, the relationship among these elements is identified to be cyclic. The reflective activities continually deconstruct what learners have already achieved and reconstruct it. Going through these processes enables students to manage and control their learning to gain better knowledge and skills.

To achieve quality learning, learners need to exercise their behavioural and cognitive processes effectively and efficiently. These processes include resolving conflicts in learning styles and preferences, strategic options, and the material demands that they face (Rivers, 2001).

Cotterall (1995) suggests learner autonomy has gained in importance and popularity for reasons which are: philosophical, pedagogical and practical. Philosophically, learners have the right to make choices about their own learning. Helping learners to learning how to make their own choices will prepare them for a changing future. Pedagogically, learning is more effective when learners are involved in decisions about the learning process. Practically, learners feel more secure when they participate in the decision-making process.

2.5. Autonomy and genders

Nunan (1988) argues that it is not absolute that all learners will develop autonomy in the same way and to the same degree. He asserts that there are degrees of autonomy, and to what extent learners develop it depends on many factors like genders of the learners, the personality of the learner, the goals of language learning, etc.

Although traditionally females and males are assumed to have different abilities regarding language, language learning and different analytical and mathematical skills, recent research studies have begun to refute this mainstream thinking. For instance, in relation to girls' and boys' self-conceptualization, Marsh, Byrne and Shavelson (1988) demonstrated that girls had a high self-concept of verbal skills and high achievement in terms of verbal skills, while boys had only a high self-concept of mathematical skills but low achievement. Different ways of learning are studied between men and women. Males are usually more field-independent and females are more field-dependent (Good & Brophy, 1987; Shipman, Krantz, & Silver, 1992). Females are more likely than males in using thinking approach (analytic, impersonal, objective, and factual) and feeling approach (emotional, personal, subjective, and empathic) Nevertheless, the mainstream research focusing on the relationship between genders and second language learning has proved some differences between sexes. In their study of females' and males' attitudes toward second language learning, Gardner and Lambert (1972) observed that not only females had more positive attitudes toward the speakers of a second language but also they were more motivated toward learning a second language than males were. Green and Oxford (1995) investigated the effects of gender and proficiency level on strategy use of EFL students. They found that learner strategies were used more by women than men, and more among successful language learners. Fourteen strategies were used significantly more often by women in this study, although only one was used significantly more often by men: watching television programs and video movies in English. Ehrman and Oxford (1989) also discovered significant gender differences in favor of women in terms of general study strategies, strategies for authentic language use, strategies for searching for and communicating meaning, and metacognitive or self-management strategies. Arabski (1999) also investigated the gender differences in language learning strategy use in a pilot study with 60 students and found out that the girls differed in their strategy use with regard to finding out about language learning, asking for correction, keeping English diaries, watching TV show and movies in English, starting conversations in English and looking for opportunities to speak in English.

McCaulley (1990) believed that females have a higher degree of empathy and (skills in) cooperative learning. Also, females tend to use social and affective strategies more often than males (Oxford, Park-Oh, Ito, & Sumrall, 1993). Oxford (1995) claims that males are somewhat more logically minded in processing language, while females behave more field-sensitive, globally-patterned, subjective, and emotional.

2.6. Autonomy and individual learning styles

The levels of learning autonomy vary greatly among varieties of learners. Many studies have been conducted to investigate the demographic characteristics which affect learners' capacity to learn (Carr, 1999; Derrick, 2001; Meyer, 2001; Ng, 2009; Ng & Confessore, 2010; Park, 1998; Ponton, 1999)

According to Confessore and Confessore (1994), autonomous learning manifests in individuals who feel the need to learn. Such people also utilize both internal psycho-social resources and external human and material resources to enhance their efforts. Felder

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(1996), Oladoke (2006), and Robotham (1995) indicate that high autonomous learners have the ability to utilize skills from all learning styles as they effectively process information. It appears that the number of learning styles with which individuals are comfortable is essential information in estimating the extent to which they are likely to function as relatively autonomous learners. For instance, an individual who prefers an independent learning style will work fine when being assigned to work alone. However, if a collaborative project is given, will the independent learner be inclined to participate as a team member? Learners who possess both independent and collaborative learning styles are less likely to face preference problems of completing both kinds of tasks. It is essential to understand relationships between autonomy and learning styles to determine if individuals' comfort with more learning styles is associated with their increased autonomy in learning. An improved understanding of learning styles in relation to learner autonomy would add to the knowledge base of the field.

III. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Participants

This study targets the first year students at PPA. The total number of participants is 117, from three classes that the researcher is in charge of teaching. These students come from different areas in Vietnam. Some of them come from mountainous provinces such as Ha Giang, Bac Kan, Dak Lac, Hoa Binh. Many of them are city dwellers e.g. Ha Noi, Hai Phong and Thai Nguyen cities. The most frequently observed category of Gender was male ($n = 68, 61\%$) The Frequencies and percentages are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Frequency Table for Nominal Variables

Variable	<i>n</i>	%
female	49	41.88
male	68	58.12
Missing	0	0.00
Total	117	100.0

Note. Due to rounding errors, percentages may not equal 100%.

3.2. Research design

The purposes of the current study include investigating the perceived levels of LA and factors which affect their LA. We realized that a purely quantitative methodology would be inadequate. A mixture of both quantitative and qualitative data analysis would be appropriate for the questions posited in this study. It is obvious that data produced by mixed method research (MMR) is more authenticated, replicable, valid and verifiable as compared to any other approach producing data singly. Creswell and Clark (2007: p. 5) define MMR as "it involves philosophical assumptions that guide the direction of the collection and analysis of data and the mixture of qualitative and quantitative data in a single study. Its central assertion is that the use of quantitative and qualitative approaches in combination provides a better understanding of research problems than either approach can do alone".

3.3. Data collection instruments

The instruments for data collection consist of questionnaires. There are three survey questionnaires which are used to collect data for qualitative and quantitative analysis. The first survey was self-perceived levels of learners' autonomy (see appendix 1). The questionnaire consists of 25 items, using Likert 5 points scale ranging from 1 (never true to me) to 5 (always true to me). There are three levels of autonomy for learners; (1) Low (mean = 1.0-2.4) (2) Medium (mean = 2.5-3.4) and (3) High (mean = 3.5-5.0). The second questionnaire was design to determine levels of teachers' promotion for students' autonomy (see appendix 2). The questionnaire consists of 20 items, using Likert 5 points scale ranging from 1 (never true to me) to 5 (always true to me). Teachers' levels of support for learners' autonomy ranges from (1) Low supportive (mean = 1.0-2.4), to (2) Medium supportive (mean = 2.5-3.4), and to High supportive (mean = 3.5-5.0). The last survey was a self-rating "Perceptual Learning Style Preference Questionnaire" and a scoring instruction so that students could figure out their preferred learning styles. The category of learning styles consists of (1) Visual, (2) Tactile, (3) Auditory, (4) Kinesthetic, (5) Group, and (6) Individual.

IV. RESEARCH FINDINGS

4.1. Research question 1

What are the perceived levels of autonomy of the first year non-English major students at the People's Police Academy?

After the data about the self- perceived learners' autonomy have been collected, the researcher used the software SPSS version 20 to analyze the data. The figures in table 2 below show the mean of self-perceived learners' autonomy was $M = 2.66$. The minimum level was 1.72. The maximum level was 3.40. Table 2 below shows the descriptive statistics of the self-perceived learners' autonomy.

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Table 2: Descriptive statistics of the self-perceived learners' autonomy

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Learner autonomy	117	1.72	3.40	2.6677	.34451
Valid N (listwise)	117				

4.2. Research question 2

What are the students' perceptions towards the roles of teachers in fostering their autonomy?

After the data about the students' perceptions towards the roles of teachers in fostering their autonomy, the researcher used the software SPSS version 20 to analyze the data. The figures in table 3 below show the mean of teachers' supportive levels was $M = 3.29$. The minimum level was 2.45. The maximum level was 3.95.

Table 3: Descriptive statistics of the teachers' supportive levels

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Teacher support	117	2.45	3.95	3.2940	.27348
Valid N (listwise)	117				

4.3. Research question 3

Is there a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between genders?

A two-tailed independent samples t-test was conducted to examine whether the mean of learners' autonomy was significantly different between the male and female categories of gender.

Results

The result of the two-tailed independent samples t-test was not significant based on an alpha value of 0.05, $t(218) = -0.70$, $p = .482$, indicating the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This finding suggests the mean of learners' autonomy was not significantly different between the male and female categories of gender. The results are presented in Table 4 and Table 5 below.

Table 4: Two-Tailed Independent Samples t-Test for learners' autonomy by gender

Group Statistics					
Variable	Gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Learner autonomy	Male	68	2.6671	.36994	.04486
	Female	49	2.6686	.30952	.04422

Table 5: Results of independent Sample t-test for learners' autonomy by gender

Independent Samples Test

		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
Learner autonomy	Equal variances assumed	3.260	.074	-.023	115	.981	-.00151	.06484	-.12994	.12692
	Equal variances not assumed			-.024	112.375	.981	-.00151	.06299	-.12631	.12329

4.4. Research question 4

Is there a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between students with different learning styles?

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was conducted to determine whether there were significant differences in learners' autonomy by learning styles.

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Results

The ANOVA was examined based on an alpha value of 0.05. The results of the ANOVA were not significant, $F = 0.600$, $p = .199$, indicating the differences in learners' autonomy among the different learning styles were significant. The means and standard deviations are presented in Table 6.

Table 6: Analysis of Variance Table for learners' autonomy by learning styles

ANOVA					
Learner autonomy					
	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	.363	5	.073	.600	.700
Within Groups	13.405	111	.121		
Total	13.768	116			

Table 7 below shows the frequencies and percentages of learning styles of the participants. Figure 8 below show the difference in learners' autonomy by learning styles

Table 7: frequencies and percentages of learning styles of the participants

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Visual	30	25.6	25.6	25.6
	Tactile	24	20.5	20.5	46.2
	Auditory	19	16.2	16.2	62.4
	Kinesthetic	14	12.0	12.0	74.4
	Group	21	17.9	17.9	92.3
	Individual	9	7.7	7.7	100.0
	Total	117	100.0	100.0	

Post Hoc Tests

Paired t-tests were calculated between each pair of measurements to further examine the differences among the variables. Tukey pairwise comparisons were conducted for all significant effects based on an alpha of 0.05. For the main effect of learning styles, the mean of learners' autonomy for visual learners ($M = 2.606$) was significantly smaller than for kinesthetic learners ($M = 2.757$). For the main effect of learning styles, the mean of learners' autonomy for individual learners ($M = 2.59$) was significantly smaller than for group and kinesthetic learners ($M = 2.72$ and $M = 2.75$ respectively). No other significant effects were found.

Table 9 below summarize descriptive statistics about variables in the study; the teachers' supportive levels, learners' autonomy, learning styles and genders

Table 9: Summary of the variables in the study

Descriptive Statistics					
	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Teacher support	117	2.45	3.95	3.2940	.27348
Learner autonomy	117	1.72	3.40	2.6677	.34451
Learning styles	117	1	6	2.99	1.669
Gender	117	1	2	1.42	.495
Valid N (listwise)	117				

V. DISCUSSIONS AND CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study reveal that the level of learners' autonomy where the study was conducted was at medium level ($M = 2.66$ out of 5.0 scale). The result is the self-perception of the students so it might be somewhat subjective. However, we can see that this level of autonomy should be higher so that students may take responsibility for their own language learning process. Gadamer (2001) said that education was self-education. It means that "self-education" eventually takes over: with a capacity for critical reflection and awareness, choices are self-weighed, decisions are self-made, pragmatic control is taken on as learners self-educate themselves to communicate in the other language. The autonomous learners are not only better in dealing with in-class tasks but also coping with out-of-classroom situations.

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In terms of the students' perception of their teachers' roles in fostering students' autonomy, the finding of the current study reveals that it was quite supportive ($M = 3.29$ out of 5.0 scale). Again, this was the students' self-evaluation. However, it was quite encouraging for teachers of English where the study was conducted. It is undeniable that when teachers are supportive in their teaching, especially encouraging learners in self-regulation and self-control of their learning process, the learning outcomes would be excellent.

The third finding of the study showed that the difference in level of autonomy is not significant between male and female students ($M = 2.667$ for male compared with $M = 2.668$ for female students). This is similar to many other studies in the regions (Yilmaz & Varol, 2010; Lu & Fan, 2013; Mardjuki, 2018).

Finally, the fourth research question looks for the discrepancy in levels of autonomy among students with different learning styles. The result showed that there is a statistically significant difference in the levels of autonomy between students with different learning styles. To be specifically, the students who prefer kinesthetic learning style possess the highest level of autonomy ($M = 2.75$) compared with $M = 2.60$ and 2.59 for visual and individual learning style students. $M = 2.72$; 2.69 and 2.62 are the level of autonomy for group, tactile and auditory students respectively. Ng & Confessore (2010) conducted a study to determine the correlation between multiple learning style students and their levels of autonomy in Malaysia and found that there is a significant, positive correlation between the learning styles and learner autonomy scores. However, the learning styles in their study were determined as *Collaborative*, *Competitive*, *Dependent*, *Independent* and *Participant* learning styles.

Finally, regardless of some limitations, the researcher hopes that this would be a reference for teachers of English in general and those at the researcher's institution in understanding of learners' autonomy.

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